

Statistical Periodicity in Classical and Quantum Physics Part II

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In a previous note (1), we argued that sound wave equations (with certain boundary conditions) derived from the Boltzmann transport equation conservation relations match the form of a quantum mechanical solution of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. Furthermore, we argued that in both the sound and quantum pictures there exists a dispersion velocity $u = d/dx \ln(\text{density})$ (classical) and $u = -i d/dx \ln(W)$ where W is the wavefunction in quantum mechanics. Both represent forward backward motion at different x points. Thus, there seems to be a link between classical sound and quantum mechanics at least in terms of some density type solutions and a backwards forwards motion.

It is also known, however, that for the ground state of a ground oscillator, the quantum solution is of the same form as the static Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) solution $C \exp(-mv^2/2mT - .5kxx/T)$. In this case, quantum mechanics still has a dispersion velocity with forward backward motion, but statistical mechanics has a zero $u(x,t)$. The Boltzmann transport conservation relations yield the MB solution on the basis of a balance of pressure and force. This leads to the question: Why do the two approaches yield the same solution in this one case, even though the underlying physics seems to be quite different? We argue that even though $u(x,t)=0$ for the MB static solution, there is still dispersive flow which is forward at the left endpoint and backwards at the right. Thus, in both the case of sound and the MB solution with a potential there may be dispersion which has links to quantum mechanics.

Sound Waves in a Statistical Gas

It possible to write the mass and momentum conservation relationships from the Boltzmann transport equation (2) i.e.

$$d/dt (\text{partial}) \text{density} + d/dx \{ \text{density } u \} = 0 \quad ((1a)) \text{ and}$$

$$(d/dt (\text{partial}) + u d/dx) u = \text{density } F/ m - d/dx \{ \text{density } [\langle vv \rangle - u u] \} \quad ((1b))$$

where $u = \langle v \rangle$ and F is force.

To obtain a sound wave equation, one assumes u and derivatives of u and density are small, but density is not. Derivatives d/dx or d/dt of density* u treat density as a constant to first order. In addition, $\langle vv \rangle$ is considered to be proportional to temperature T and its derivatives are ignored i.e. it is treated as a constant. This leads to:

$$d/dt d/dt \text{density} + cc d/dx d/dx \text{density} = 0 \quad ((2)) \text{ i.e a wave equation.}$$

Treating density as separable in x and t , leads to an x only equation which with boundary conditions may describe standing sound waves.

First, we wish to point out that ((2)) is a time-dependent equation even if one has standing waves. A similar result holds for waves on a string. This is analogous to the factor $\exp(iEt)$ in quantum mechanics, we argue. $\exp(iEt)$ does not appear in the density $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$, but that does not change time cycling motion just as in the classical sound or string wave problem.

The second issue is to note that for both quantum mechanics and sound, u is a dispersion velocity which represents both forward and backward motion. For the approximations used to obtain the sound wave equation, ((1a)) and ((1b)) become:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial density} + \text{density} \frac{d}{dx} u = 0 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{density} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} u + C \frac{d}{dx} \text{density} = 0 \quad ((3b))$$

This suggests that a small x,t solution of u is Cxt as noted in (1) which is analogous to $\sin(at)\sin(bx) / [\cos(at)\cos(bx)]$. Examining ((3b)) shows that $u(x,t)$ is of the form $c \frac{d}{dx} \text{density} / \text{density}$ which is a dispersion velocity. Given that $\text{density} = B \cos(cx)$, this velocity u is periodic in space just like the dispersion velocity in quantum mechanics $-i \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. In both cases, the dispersion velocity leads to humps forming. In the quantum case, there is a probability wave, yet forward backward motion and density humps are as physical as in the case of sound.

Stationary Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Solutions

A nonzero $u(x,t)$ holds for sound waves, but not for the usual stationary MB distribution $C \exp(-.5mvv/T -V/T)$ for which $u(x,t)=0$. If one considers the momentum conservation equation which follows from the Boltzmann transport equation (3):

$$\text{density} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} u + u \frac{d}{dx} \right) u = \text{density} / m F - \frac{d}{dx} \{ \text{density} [\langle vv \rangle - uu] \} \quad ((4)) \quad \text{in one dimension}$$

Setting $u=0$ and treating $\langle vv \rangle = T$ as a constant:

$$\text{Force} = F = T \frac{d}{dx} \text{density} / \text{density} \quad \text{or} \quad \text{density} = C \exp(-V(x)/T) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, there is a kind of dispersion velocity $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(\text{density})$, but no $u(x,t)$. ((5)) seems to be a force balance equation i.e. the gradient of pressure balancing a force as often present in texts.. In other words, this appears as a very static equation, in marked contrast to a medium with sound waves.

It may be noted that ((5)) matches a quantum mechanical solution for the ground state of an oscillator. In addition, $f(p) = B \exp(-bpp)$ which is also of a MB form, where $f(p)$ is the Fourier transform of the wavefunction $W(x)$. One may ask why a static type statistical force balance

should match a quantum probability wave type picture? In this section, we consider the static picture.

First, one may note that bound state quantum mechanics is based on average energy conservation:

$$KE(\text{ave}) + V(x) = E \text{ i.e. } -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W + V = E \quad ((6))$$

This provides a link with Force=F because one may take d/dx of ((6)) and obtain the classical looking result:

$$d/dx (KE(\text{ave}(x))) = -dV/dx = F. \quad ((7))$$

In this case, however, there is no static force balance as in statistical mechanics.

If one wishes ((7)) to match statistical mechanics then: $F = d/dx \text{ density} / \text{density} = 2 dW/dx / W$ or

$-dV/dx = 2dW/dx / W$ a solution being $W = \exp(-CV)$ where C is a constant. The problem is that $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W$ in such a case is not kinetic energy unless $-\frac{1}{2m} (-Cd/dx dV/dx) + CCdV/dx dV/dx = E - V$. $V = .5kx^2$ is a solution to this equation.

Thus, a probability type wave quantum situation with forward backward imaginary dispersion i.e. $-i dW/dx / W = \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle / m$ can create a statistical mechanical scenario for the ground state of the oscillator. A key difference between the quantum and statistical mechanical cases is that:

density $KE(\text{ave}(x)) + V(x)$ density = E density does not hold for the statistical mechanical case.

In statistical mechanics $KE(\text{ave})(x) = .5 T$ (in one dimension).

Difference in Temperatures in the Quantum and Statistical Mechanical Ground State Oscillator

It is interesting to note that the parameter T (temperature) appears in MB expression. The stochastic feature of a statistical mechanical gas is two body scattering and T is a parameter related to the average kinetic energy. If potential energy exists, it accelerates a gas particle in a classical manner. It is not treated as stochastic, unlike quantum mechanics which displays no acceleration of any $\exp(ipx)$. Only the change in conditional average kinetic energy $[\text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$ displays acceleration. Like quantum mechanics, however, there is conservation of energy, but only at a single particle level, not at an average level. Thus, there exists a two body scattering balanced reaction: $f(p1)f(p2) = f(p3)f(p4)$. Taking ln of both sides and equating to the conservation equation $p1^2/2m + p2^2/2m = p3^2/2m + p4^2/2m$ yields

$\exp(-pp/2mT)$. Applying the idea of conservation of energy $pp/2m + V=E$ to a single particle changes $pp/2mT$ into $pp/2mT + V/T$.

For an oscillator, $\text{density}(x) = \exp(-V/T)$ where $.5T$ is the one dimensional average kinetic energy. The quantum oscillator ground state density is: $\exp(-2axx)$ where $2a = 2E$ with E being total ground state energy. Thus: $\sqrt{k/m}xx = .5kxx / .5\sqrt{k/m}$. For $m=1$, $.5\sqrt{k}$ is the total energy of the ground state oscillator where T is twice the kinetic energy (1 dimension). For the oscillator, total energy is twice average kinetic energy.

Dispersion Picture

In the above section, statistical mechanical equilibrium with a potential was described in terms of a static balance of forces. There are dynamical flows, however, because the $\text{force} = -dV/dx$ accelerates particles in one direction and decelerates them in the other. Thus, densities change to counteract this asymmetry in flow. Consider:

$$d/dx \text{ density} = \text{Brownian motion term} = \{-1/T d/dx V + (dV/dx) (1/T)\} \text{density} \quad (8)$$

As noted, quantum mechanics combines a Brownian kinetic energy term with stochastic interactions of $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ to create a constant average E at each point x .

If one wishes ((8)) to match quantum mechanics, a possible solution is:

$$1/T d/dx V = \text{constant}^2 \text{ Energy} \quad \text{and} \quad (1/T)(1/T) dV/dx = \text{constant}^2 V$$

An oscillator potential will yield such a result. For the quantum oscillator, there is symmetry between pp and xx and $\int dx -1/2m W d/dx W = \int dp V(x) W(x) W(x) = \int dp pp^2/m f(p)f(p)$ so one may a solution with $W(x)$ and $f(p)$ having the same mathematical form holds.

It should be noted that quantum bound states usually have humps, but the ground state is often a single hump. Thus, the overall forward backward motion of dispersion seems to be present in the ground state solution with overall forward motion at the left hand boundary removing density and overall backwards motion at the right hand boundary again removing density to create a hump in the middle. Thus, even though the statistical mechanical oscillator static state is not one of a sound wave, it has dispersion with both forward and backwards motion at different x values (endpoint x values) and represents dynamic dispersion as well.

Thus, there does not seem to be a logical inconsistency in linking sound waves in a pipe with certain boundary conditions to a quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls and the quantum oscillator ground state with the MB distribution $\exp(-.5mvv/T - V/T)$ which is usually described as static, but can also be thought of in terms of diffusion velocities and dispersion.

Adding Sound Waves to a Statistical Mechanical Oscillator

The static $\exp(-.5mvv/T - V/T)$ statistical mechanical oscillator solution should allow for the addition of sound waves. These would partially mimic excited quantum oscillator states. Consider:

Density = $\exp(-V/T) + d^2$ where d^2 is small and let u and its derivatives also be small. Then:

$$d/dt (\text{partial}) d^2 + d/dx \{(\exp(-V/T) u)\} = 0 \quad ((9a))$$

$$\text{And } (\exp(-V/T) d/dt \text{ partial } u = aT d/dx d^2 \quad ((9b))$$

If one treats $\exp(-V/T)$ as close to 1 i.e. a very weak oscillator then ((9a)) and ((9b)) can be converted into the standard sound differential equation, which is not a surprise (given that the potential has been basically removed).

Consider the quantum oscillator wavefunction as: $\exp(-V/2T) W^2$. Then:

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx W^2 - 1/m (d/dx \exp(-V/2T))(d/dx W^2) / \exp(-V/2T) = (\text{delta } E) W^2$$

If $V/2T$ changes very slowly and $\exp(-V/2T)$ is almost 1, then dV/dx is small and one has the equation for a particle in a box i.e. a sound type of equation.

Although the above example is not practical, it seems to suggest that sound or sound type solutions can be added to create excited states. Again, the above is hand-wavy, but we wish to combine the idea of sound (a very wavelike dispersion velocity) with a ground state which may only have considerable dispersion near the endpoints.

Conclusion

In this note, we argue that both sound and static Maxwell-Boltzmann distributions $\exp(-.5mvv/T - V/T)$ are based on dispersion (diffusion) velocities. In the case of sound, there is an explicit $u=Cxt$ for tiny x, t in the mass and momentum conservation Boltzmann transport equations. This, in turn, is equivalent to a dispersion velocity of $d/dx \text{ density} / \text{density}$ and matches ideas related to a quantum bound particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. There is forward backward motion in $u(x,t)$ which leads to humps.

For the case of a ground state oscillator, for which statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics have similar momentum and space densities, the traditional statistical mechanical approach is to balance the gradient of pressure with force. Formally, $u(x,t)$ is 0, but it seems there are still various asymmetric flows in the system which overall give the appearance of $u(x,t)=0$. We argue that there exists dispersion i.e. the force accelerates particles to the right

and left creating a flow asymmetry This is balanced by a nonconstant spatial density which drops to zero at the endpoints. We argue there is net dispersion forwards at the left hand boundary and backwards at the right i.e. $d/dx \text{ density} / \text{density} = F=-kx$. Thus, even the “static” case may be viewed as having a dispersion velocity with forward/ backward motion which mimics quantum mechanics.

Thus, it seems that not only classical sound solutions, but also the “static” Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for an oscillator potential may mimic the quantum picture of diffusion flows with forward and backwards motion at different x points. In the case of the oscillator density, there is a single Gaussian hump.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Statistical Periodicity in Classical and Quantum Physics (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1983)